

Reading performance of alpine schoolchildren in relationship to physical, social, and perceptual characteristics of the home and school environments

Angel M. Dzhambov^{a,b,1,*}, Peter Lercher^{c,1}, Jan Spilski^d, Johannes Rüdiger^e,
Matthew H.E.M. Browning^f, Iana Markevych^{a,g,h}

^a Environmental Health Division, Research Institute at Medical University of Plovdiv, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

^b Institute of Highway Engineering and Transport Planning, Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria

^c Independent Researcher

^d Center for Cognitive Science, Department of Cognitive and Developmental Psychology, University of Kaiserslautern-Landau, Germany

^e Department of Ecology, University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria

^f Department of Parks, Recreation and Tourism Management, Clemson University, Clemson, SC, USA

^g Health and Quality of Life in a Green and Sustainable Environment Research Group, Strategic Research and Innovation Program for the Development of MU – Plovdiv, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

^h Institute of Psychology, Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to examine the relationships between the physical, social, and perceptual characteristics of the home and school environments and children's reading performance. A cross-sectional sample of 1251 8-12-year-old schoolchildren from the Tyrol region of Austria and Italy was analyzed. Reading performance was measured based on the number of correctly read sentences in 3 min. Teacher ratings of self-regulation and inattention, child reports of the restorative quality and safety of the residential area, and good family relations, as reported by mothers were also considered. Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors were obtained from mother questionnaires, and secondhand smoke exposure of the child was measured by cotinine in urine. A built environment score was constructed using imperviousness density, modeled traffic noise, and air pollution. Landscape diversity and natural surroundings around the school, and the presence of a domestic garden represented directly accessible nature. Structural equation modeling was used to examine the relationships between these variables. A positive parent-child relationship, higher maternal education, better self-regulation, being female, lower cotinine, and a greater level of school natural land use were associated with better reading performance. These associations were mediated by a combination of factors, including higher neighborhood safety and inattention. There was a positive association between reading and being native German speaker in North Tyrol. Exposure to the built environment and the absence of a domestic garden were also associated with better reading. Understanding local socioeconomic, land use, and cultural patterns can help better explain complex observed associations.

1. Introduction

More than 600 million children worldwide are lacking minimum proficiency levels in reading (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2017) and 7.1 % of primary school children have developmental dyslexia (Yang et al., 2022). A decline in reading literacy is not limited to lower income countries, rather it is observed in European countries as well, though

with considerable variations (OECD, 2023). Currently, in Austria and Italy, 29 % and 35 % of adults, respectively, have low literacy proficiency, struggling to understand longer texts with distracting information (OECD, 2024a, 2024b). However, a trend toward decreasing reading performance in these countries was noted already in the period 2000–2006, according to the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (OECD, 2008). Reading ability is one of the main

* Corresponding author. Environmental Health Division, Research Institute at Medical University of Plovdiv, Medical University of Plovdiv, 15A Vasil Aprilov Blvd, 4002, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

E-mail addresses: angelletoti@gmail.com, angel.dzhambov@mu-plovdiv.bg (A.M. Dzhambov).

¹ Equal first co-authorship.

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skills taught to children in the first years of school education. It is a product of complex cognitive processes such as language comprehension, word recognition, as well as background knowledge and self-regulatory faculties (Duke and Cartwright, 2021). Decades of research have shown that poor reading performance in the early school years continues into the later school years and predicts reading and math achievement tests (Duncan et al., 2007). However, reading difficulties not only undermine academic success but correlate with cognitive and psycho-emotional problems (Carroll et al., 2005; Daniel et al., 2006; Maughan and Carroll, 2006; Mugnaini et al., 2009). Beyond the school years, reading performance may influence career paths and prospects in later life, as well as social participation and adaptation (Shulman et al., 2024).

Research across various disciplines has focused on explaining the observed individual differences in reading performance. Early behavior-genetic studies in twins have found a high percentage of heritability in poor reading performance (Harris, 1982; DeFries and Gillis, 1993). Familial dyslexia, for instance, has been found to be a significant risk factor for difficulty with reading (Torppa et al., 2022). More recent longitudinal genome-wide association studies have extended the genetic hypothesis to encompass environmental and social factors (Andreola et al., 2021; Erbeli et al., 2021; Mascheretti et al., 2024). Social circumstances have a profound influence on developmental trajectories mostly via psychosocial stress (Evans and Schamberg, 2009). Aside from socioeconomic status and parental education, family structure and relationships, support, and involvement are critical for building self-regulatory capacities and an adaptive coping repertoire (Basu and Banerjee, 2020; Costa et al., 2024). The home literacy environment (reading aloud, shared reading, number of books at home, etc.) has been positively related to reading achievement (Burgess et al., 2002; Park, 2008; Niklas and Schneider, 2017). Children's reading and language proficiency can also differ depending on their biological sex, with girls generally outperforming boys (Manu et al., 2023; Voyer and Voyer, 2014).

Other individual factors that influence reading are attention and concentration. Inattention, as found in attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) for example, is associated with poorer reading and math performance (Hart et al., 2010; DuPaul et al., 2016). The ability to maintain directed attention and regulate emotions and behavior is partly contingent on the surrounding environment's potential to support renewal of adaptive capacities diminished in ongoing efforts to meet adaptive demands or rather induce stress (Hartig, 2021; Ursache et al., 2022; Dzhambov et al., 2023). An environment dominated by traffic, air, and noise pollution can constrain restoration of attentional resources and induce psychophysiological stress that adversely changes neurochemistry, while natural settings can work in the opposite direction (Dzhambov et al., 2023). A large body of evidence has linked children's exposure to air pollution to impaired learning (Roche et al., 2024). However, the associations have not always been consistent (Sunyer et al., 2015; Grineski et al., 2020; Claesen et al., 2021; Mилоjevic et al., 2021). Associations with traffic noise exposure in classrooms also differ (Klatte et al., 2013, 2017; Mealings, 2022; Gheller et al., 2023; Tangermann et al., 2023). Conversely, nature was found to support various cognitive functions (Browning and Rigolon, 2019; Buczyłowska et al., 2023). On a coarser scale, area-level differences in reading achievements can be linked to socioeconomic (Buckingham et al., 2013; Liu, 2024) and urban-rural gradients (Boman, 2022), differences in educational systems (Broer et al., 2019; Liu, 2024), and ethnic composition (Sacco and Falzetti, 2021; Boman, 2022).

Beyond the outdoor environment, indoor living conditions also matter, such as passive smoking (Yolton et al., 2005; Chen et al., 2013; Ling and Heffernan, 2016). However, previous studies either focused on maternal smoking during pregnancy or used self-report measures rather than biomarkers, and observed results were conflicting (Chen et al., 2013). Few studies have investigated reading performance in a multi-exposure framework (e.g., Kweon et al., 2017; Kuo et al., 2018; Claesen et al., 2021). For example, the elements of the social exposome,

which encapsulates demographic and socioeconomic characteristics, relational dynamics, cultural values, and social norms, embedded in higher-level social and political systems in spatially resolved patterns, have rarely received sufficient attention in the field of environmental epidemiology where they are often treated as confounding factors and merely adjusted for (Gudi-Mindermann et al., 2023). This leaves a major interdisciplinary gap in the understanding of how environmental and social influences can jointly shape the development of reading skills (cf. Persson Waye et al., 2023). Furthermore, there is not much direct evidence on specific pathways underpinning the effect of the built environment on reading, or studies on improved attention and emotion-regulation as pathways, or studies on the combined effect of natural and built environment components, or on child experiences and perceptions of their surroundings (Buczyłowska et al., 2023). Children quite literally see the world from a perspective different from that of adults (Langley et al., 2023). How children perceive their physical surroundings, such as their neighborhood, seems to explain much of the associations with well-being (Lercher et al., 2025), and is distinctly associated with child mental well-being compared with parental perceptions (Côté-Lussier et al., 2015; Infantino et al., 2024). Specifically, general environmental quality encompassing aspects like restorative capacity and safety can support physical activity (McDonald et al., 2015; Hayball et al., 2018) and mental health (Meltzer et al., 2007). Individual differences related to environmental perceptions, such as noise sensitivity, can also change the way children react to and are affected by their surroundings (Heinonen-Guzejev, 2009; Hill, 2012). Overall, the relationships of the factors underlying reading difficulties are complex and variable (Roche et al., 2024). Moreover, extant research is mainly based on dichotomous dyslexia diagnoses and not on reading performance, where dyslexia represents only the left tail of normally distributed reading abilities (Shaywitz et al., 1992; Elliott and Grigorenko, 2024).

Drawing on available data for Austrian and Italian schoolchildren (Lercher et al., 2025) and guided by the Bronfenbrenner ecological model (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 1998), in this study we adopted a broader approach to investigating the internal, social, and external influences on reading performance, using child, parent, and teacher assessments. We aimed to test the hypothesis that the built environment, traffic-related emissions, and passive smoking are adversely associated with reading performance, while nature availability and positive family relationships are protectively associated with it. Further, we hypothesized that these associations are mediated by child perceptions, inattention, and self-regulation, and can vary geographically.

2. Methods

2.1. Sampling and study area

A cross-sectional sample of 1251 children aged 8–12 years from 3rd and 4th grade was collected for the study. Children were recruited in 2004–2005 from 49 randomly selected public schools located in the Tyrol region of Austria and Italy, North and South Tyrol, respectively (Fig. 1). The study area encompassed several alpine valleys, including the Lower Inn valley, the Wipp valley, and three additional side valleys that extended radially from the Wipp valley. The area is predominantly unurbanized, characterized by substantial traffic congestion along the Lower Inn and Wipp valley floors and a notable presence of dense vegetation on the mountain slopes. Meteorological conditions and local topography vary across these valleys, leading to differential patterns of sound propagation and air pollution dispersion. For a comprehensive overview of the study's design and setting, refer to the work of Dzhambov et al. (2019).

Information obtained from reading tests administered at school was combined with child and mother-reports and teacher assessments of child performance. Subsequently, these data were linked to geographic variables that characterized the built and natural environments in the home and school areas. Ethical approval for this study was obtained

Fig. 1. Map of the study area. Note. The solid black line represents the borders of Austria splitting the study area into North (in Austria) and South Tyrol (in Italy). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

from the Ethics Committee of the Medical University Innsbruck (Ethics Commission number 2105/2004).

2.2. Reading performance outcome

At the time the study was conducted, only two German-language procedures for assessment of reading had been sufficiently psychometrically validated: the Würzburg Quiet Reading Test (Würzburger Leise Leseprobe) (Küspert and Schneider, 1998) and the Salzburg Reading Screening (Salzburger Lesescreening) (Mayringer and Wimmer, 2003). The Salzburg Reading Screening was preferred due to its efficiency in terms of administration time, its higher ecological validity in reading skills, and its better capacity to differentiate reading performance in older children (up to the age of 11) within the higher performance range. The test gauges the so-called basal reading skills (Mayringer and Wimmer, 2003), which encompasses reading speed and, indirectly, reading accuracy. In the study, we consistently used test version A1, which is used for screening and uses simple sentences.

Briefly, in one of the children's regular classes, a psychologist, who had also administered pretests on children of this age group, provided instructions. Thereafter, the children were presented with a list of 70 sentences containing fundamental world knowledge. The test task entailed the silent reading of each individual sentence and the subsequent evaluation of its content as either correct or incorrect, indicated by a tick or a cross mark, respectively, next to each sentence. The processing time to verify the veracity of as many of the sentences as possible was 3 min. The most important test value is the number of sentences that can be read correctly within the time limit (Mayringer and Wimmer, 2003), and it was standardized and thus employed as the outcome measure in the analyses.

2.3. Built environment and greenspace exposures

Traffic-related noise and air pollution were calculated at the residential address coordinates using modeling techniques that were tailored to the unique characteristics of the study area. A detailed description of the models can be found elsewhere (Dzhambov et al., 2019). Exposure to traffic-related air pollution was represented by the

mean annual concentration of nitrogen dioxide (NO_2). It was calculated using a meteorological model, the Graz Mesoscale Model, at a horizontal resolution of 10×10 m and a vertical resolution of 2 m. Day-evening-night sound levels (L_{den}) for each address were determined by assigning traffic noise levels from highways, other roads, and railway traffic in the valleys. NO_2 and L_{den} were combined in a latent variable together with the percentage of artificially sealed soil in a 100-m buffer area around the home address, as greyspace or built-up area indicator. These imperviousness density (0–100 %) data were obtained at a spatial resolution of 20×20 m from the Copernicus repository (<https://land.copernicus.eu/user-corner/technical-library/hrl-imperviousness-technical-document-prod-2015>).

The potentially positive influence of residential greenspace on reading performance was represented by the presence of a structured **domestic garden** reported by the child's mother (cf. van Lier et al., 2017). In this study context, gardens encompassed private green spaces, green yards, orchards, floral gardens, and vegetable gardens. Garden presence was used in lieu of a satellite-based greenness indicator for two reasons. First, satellite-based greenness exhibits excessive correlation with the imperviousness density indicator in the area (Lercher et al., 2025). And second, the vegetation biomass across the entire study area is uniformly very high and does not necessarily reflect differences in its function and actual usage.

In addition to a home-centered greenspace variable, we measured the degree of naturalness and landscape diversity in a 250 m Euclidean buffer radius around the school building. The median distance between a home location and the nearest school was about 554 m. The 250 m buffer size was expected to capture surrounding outdoor areas where school children practice outdoor sports or walk, and to cover roughly half of the median distance to the home. Landscape diversity indicators were used as a proxy for biodiversity, which expands the framework of the greenspace – health relationship (Marselle et al., 2021). The **naturalness** scale was based on classes of groups 3 (forests and semi-natural lands), 4 (wetlands), and 5 (water bodies) from the first level of the CORINE Land Cover legend. The data were sourced from the Copernicus CLC dataset for the year 2000 (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover/clc-2000>). The concept of naturalness was operationalized through the calculation of the ratio between natural land

cover and the total area, with values ranging from 0 (low naturalness) to 1 (high naturalness). The assessment of **landscape diversity** was informed by land cover data pertaining to classes within group 300 (forests and semi-natural lands), 400 (wetlands), and 500 (water bodies) from the third level of the CLC legend. This approach was based on the hypothesis that each one of these land use classes can hold distinct contingent of species. This indicator ranges from 0, representing one land cover type, to 1, representing six land cover types (Gardi et al., 2010).

2.4. Perceived neighborhood characteristics as pathways

A series of questions was used to assess children's perceptions of their neighborhood environment. The questions addressed available infrastructure, the function of places, and safety. From these, we constructed two scales. The scale we developed to measure **perceived neighborhood quality** comprised of seven items, where higher values indicate higher neighborhood quality. Some of these items are semantically similar to items from the Perceived Restorativeness Scale for Children (Berto et al., 2015). The children were asked to rate their neighborhood based on various factors, including the availability of open spaces for play, the presence of meadows and trees, air quality, the level of noise, the allowance for unstructured play, the helpfulness of the residents towards children, and the overall enjoyment of living in the neighborhood. Responses were given on a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 4 (1 = not right at all, 2 = rather not right, 3 = rather right, 4 = fully right). The internal consistency of this scale was deemed acceptable, with a McDonald's omega value of 0.70.

A **traffic safety scale** was constructed by summing up the responses to three items on perceived danger and fear from traffic on the way to school (Lercher et al., 2025). Responses were given on the same four-point Likert scale. On this scale, higher values indicate higher levels of perceived traffic safety. McDonald's value of 0.55 for this scale was not ideal.

2.5. Inattention and self-regulation as pathways

The construct of **inattention** was measured using a set of four items drawn from the Needleman questionnaire on school behavior (Needleman et al., 1979). School teachers evaluated the presence or absence of inattention symptoms using items that semantically captured DSM-5 (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) inattention criteria for the diagnosis of ADHD. These included the following: easy distractibility during work; ability to persist with a task (reversed); disorganization; and daydreaming. The scale ranges from 0 to 4, with higher values indicating higher inattention. The McDonald's omega coefficient for this scale was 0.78. The internal consistency was therefore considered acceptable.

Self-regulation was examined using two additional items from the Needleman questionnaire. Teachers reported on whether children were overly excitable and impulsive, as well as whether they became frustrated easily by difficulties. These two items were moderately correlated ($r_{\text{poly}} = 0.47$) and were combined to measure **poor emotional self-regulation**.

2.6. Family relations as a pathway

Two items reflecting **good family relations** during the previous week were extracted from the KINDL questionnaire (Ravens-Sieberer and Bullinger, 1998). Parental responses to these items, asking whether the child got well with the parents and felt good at home, were evaluated by the mother on a five-point scale from 1 = never to 5 = very often. The correlation between these items was $r_{\text{poly}} = 0.73$ and they were summed into a scale.

2.7. Passive smoking as a pathway

Cotinine measured in children's 12 h urine served as a biomarker of secondhand smoke exposure (Haufrond and Lison, 1998; Boyaci et al., 2006). The mother was instructed on the proper protocol for collecting 12 h overnight urine samples. This was to be done in the morning using 10-ml monovettes. The sample was promptly returned to its original container and stored in the freezer compartment at home. At the laboratory, samples that were not analyzed within 2 h were stored at a temperature of -80°C . Samples were defrosted at a temperature of $+4^{\circ}\text{C}$ and subsequently brought to room temperature. The absorbencies of the samples were measured at dual wavelengths of 450 nm and 650 nm, employing a Microplate Scanning Spectro-photometer from Bio-Tek Instruments. The analysis was conducted using Cotinine Direct ELISA Kits (BQ086D, LOT: EK2072, ED: 11/06) from BioQuant. This method of cotinine measurement yielded a limit of detection of 0.7 ng/dl. Concentrations are expressed in micro-moles per milligram of creatinine to compensate for variations in urine density (Boeniger et al., 1993; Muscat et al., 2011).

2.8. Other covariates

Information pertaining to potential confounding factors and effect modifiers was obtained through questionnaires completed by both children and their mothers. The sociodemographic variables included in the study encompassed the child's age, sex, and maternal education, which were reported by the mother. Maternal education was categorized as follows: basic for ≤ 9 years of school, skilled labor, vocational, and higher/A-level. This categorization served as a proxy for the family's socioeconomic status. The child's noise sensitivity was reported on a single-item five-point scale (1 = not at all to 5 = very much). Furthermore, an indicator variable was created to denote the geographic region where the child resided, distinguishing between 0 = South and 1 = North Tyrol.

2.9. Statistical analysis

A descriptive analysis of the variables was conducted to identify missing values and check distributional assumptions. Because the percentage of missing data was relatively low ($< 4\%$), complete case analyses were deemed appropriate. Consequently, the analytic sample varied across analyses. Reading performance was normally distributed; however, other variables were ordered categorical. Therefore, a polychoric correlation matrix was constructed to examine the patterns of associations between the outcome, mediator, and predictor variables. These correlations were also stratified by North vs. South Tyrol.

Then, we tested a path model developed drawing on theory and earlier findings based on this dataset (Dzhambov et al., 2022; Lercher et al., 2025) (see Fig. 2 and Table S1). It was assumed that reading performance would be negatively affected by built environmental exposures (air pollution, noise, and imperviousness) around the home, and positively affected by having a domestic garden, and by greater naturalness and landscape diversity surrounding the school ("school nature"). Moreover, it was assumed that these effects would be carried through perceived environmental characteristics (perceived neighborhood quality, perceived safety), and in turn inattention and self-regulation. That is, built environment would be associated with more negative perceived environmental characteristics, and in turn with higher inattention and poorer self-regulation, while domestic garden and school nature would work in the positive direction. Noise sensitivity would also be negatively associated with environmental perceptions and reading. On the other hand, good family relations would be associated with better self-regulation and less inattention, and then with better reading performance. Tyrol region, social circumstances, and socio-demographic indicators, were expected to work in parallel with the physical exposures and family relations. However, for the directionality

Fig. 2. Conceptual model of the hypothesized associations between the physical, social, and perceptual characteristics of the home and school environments and children's reading performance. Note. Green lines represent hypothesized positive associations, orange lines represent inverse associations, and black lines represent either positive or inverse associations. Some factors appear multiple times in the figure for presentational clarity. Ovals enclose latent variable scores, and squares enclose observed variables/scores. See [Supplementary Table S1](#) for a justification of these paths. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

of some associations with Tyrol region, sex, maternal education, and German tongue we did not hold strong a priori expectations.

We employed structural equation modeling (SEM) to test whether this model could be reproduced by the available data. The model's measurement component included the built environment, school nature, and inattention as latent variables. Since the variables in the model were not multivariate normally distributed, the solution was estimated using a diagonally weighted least squares (DWLS) estimator (DiStefano and Morgan, 2014). Robust standard errors were implemented for the regression path coefficients. Pairwise deletion was used for missing data and each covariance was estimated using all available pairs. The standard errors for the defined parameters representing indirect mediation paths (i.e., the product of the path coefficients associated with their components) were computed using the delta method, for computational efficiency (Sobel, 1982). Presence of indirect effects was assumed when the 95 % confidence interval around the estimate did not contain zero. A priori, covariances between NO_2 and L_{den} , built environment and school nature, and perceived neighborhood quality and traffic safety were assumed. After inspection of the modification indices from the initial solution to improve the model's fit, the model was re-fitted, adding empirically indicated and theoretically consistent covariances between domestic garden and school nature, maternal education and region, and family relations and traffic safety. To explore potential region-specific effects, a multi-group model stratified by Tyrol region was also fitted.

The evaluation of model fit was conducted using a set of widely applied indices and their corresponding cut-off criteria proposed by Hu and Bentler (1999). These criteria include a non-significant χ^2 statistic ($p > 0.05$), a comparative fit index (CFI) of ≥ 0.95 , a root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) of ≤ 0.06 with a 90 % CI of ≤ 0.06 , and a standardized root mean squared residual (SRMR) of ≤ 0.08 . A parsimony normed fit index (PNFI), which accounts for the complexity of the model, was expected to exceed 0.50 (Iacobucci, 2010).

We refrained from referring to dichotomized statistical significance of the point estimates when interpreting the results of this epidemiological study, despite the formally accepted alpha level of 0.05 for the tests. The primary focus was on the direction, magnitude, consistency, and precision of the coefficients (Amrhein et al., 2019, 2019; Wasserstein and Lazar, 2016; 2019). The analyses were conducted using StataMP 19 (StataCorp, 2025) and lavaan 0.6–19 (Rossee, 2012) for R 4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024).

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics and correlations

The total sample encompassed 1251 children, with an average age of approximately 9 years and a predominantly equal distribution of females and males (Table 1). The children resided in areas characterized by diverse socioeconomic and environmental conditions. The majority of the children resided in North Tyrol. North Tyrol children exhibited superior reading performance. Moreover, their parents more often reported good family dynamics. A higher proportion of children from North Tyrol were born to mothers with a high level of education and training in skilled labor, as opposed to those with a basic level of education. The levels of traffic noise were higher in the north, and schools were surrounded by less natural land. However, NO_2 levels were lower, and children reported higher perceived neighborhood quality and lower noise sensitivity. Some of these differences were subtle though.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, reading performance exhibited a negative correlation with inattention, poor self-regulation, and male sex. A positive correlation was observed between being native German speaker, living in North Tyrol, maternal education, and reading performance. The built environment was correlated with perceptions of lower neighborhood quality and safety. Conversely, more natural land use and domestic gardens were associated with the opposite correlations. Being native German speaker was associated with more favorable environmental and psychological variables.

Upon stratification by region, differential correlation patterns were observed between North and South Tyrol (Figs. S1 and S2). In the south, higher maternal education was associated with living in a more urbanized area with higher levels of traffic emissions and imperviousness and fewer gardens. Furthermore, in the south, native German origin was associated with lower maternal education, but not with reading. In contrast, in the north, native German-speaking children had better reading performance, and their mothers had higher education.

3.2. Structural equation modeling

Structural equation modeling (SEM) was deemed an appropriate follow-up to the correlations. The model was fitted on 1251 children. It converged after 77 iterations and exhibited an adequate fit to the data: $\chi^2_{(129)} = 333.79$, $p < 0.001$; CFI = 0.96; RMSEA = 0.04 (90 % CI: 0.03, 0.04), SRMR = 0.04; and PNFI = 0.58. A significant χ^2 , although not preferred, is to be expected with a fairly large sample size, while the

Table 1
Participant characteristics across Tyrol.

Characteristics	Valid N	Total sample (N = 1251)	Geographic region	
			South Tyrol (N = 348)	North Tyrol (N = 903)
Sociodemographic factors				
Age [years]	1251	9.36 ± 0.65	9.05 ± 0.61	9.48 ± 0.63
Female sex	1251	628 (50.20 %)	178 (51.15 %)	450 (49.83 %)
Native German tongue: Yes	1240	1116 (90.00 %)	310 (90.64 %)	806 (89.76 %)
Maternal education	1209			
Basic		279 (23.08 %)	109 (32.73 %)	170 (19.41 %)
Skilled labor		396 (32.75 %)	70 (21.02 %)	326 (37.21 %)
Vocational		287 (23.74 %)	84 (25.23 %)	203 (23.17 %)
A-level		247 (20.43 %)	70 (21.02 %)	177 (20.21 %)
Reading performance [z-score]	1245	-0.04 (-0.65, 0.67)	-0.29 (-0.86, 0.34)	0.08 (-0.64, 0.78)
Perceptual factors				
Inattention [0-4]	1220	0.00 (0.00, 2.00)	0.00 (0.00, 2.00)	0.00 (0.00, 2.00)
Poor self-regulation [0-2]	1231	0.00 (0.00, 1.00)	0.00 (0.00, 1.00)	0.00 (0.00, 1.00)
Good family relations [2-10]	1237	10.00 (9.00, 10.00)	9.00 (8.00-10.00)	10.00 (9.00, 10.00)
Perceived neighborhood quality [10-28]	1215	24.00 (22.00, 26.00)	24.00 (21.00, 26.00)	25.00 (22.00, 27.00)
Perceived safety [3-12]	1236	9.00 (8.00, 11.00)	10.00 (8.00-11.00)	9.00 (8.00, 11.00)
Noise sensitivity [1-5]	1237	2.00 (1.00, 2.00)	2.00 (1.00, 2.00)	1.00 (1.00, 2.00)
Physical environment factors				
Built environment				
L_{den} [dB]	1251	49.89 (42.54, 59.54)	47.58 (41.61-55.81)	50.75 (43.00, 60.63)
NO_2 [$\mu g/m^3$]	1251	14.35 (9.86, 22.19)	15.85 (8.00-18.29)	12.69 (9.95, 24.48)
Imperviousness [0-100 %]	1251	26.31 (8.81, 46.84)	26.34 (4.38-46.49)	26.31 (10.46, 47.04)
School nature				
Naturalness [0-1]	1251	0.00 (0.00, 0.04)	0.02 (0.00, 0.09)	0.00 (0.00, 0.01)
Landscape diversity [0-1]		0.17 (0.17, 0.33)	0.33 (0.17, 0.33)	0.17 (0.17, 0.33)
Domestic garden: Yes	1239	927 (74.82 %)	251 (72.75 %)	676 (75.62 %)
Cotinine [$\mu mol/mol$]	1251	0.47 (0.12, 1.75)	0.39 (0.12, 1.42)	0.54 (0.13, 2.04)

Note. Abbreviations: L_{den} – address day-evening-night sound level from all traffic sources in dB, N – number of cases, NO_2 – annual mean nitrogen dioxide level in $\mu g/m^3$. The coefficients are mean ± standard deviation, median with 25th and 75th percentiles, or number of cases and percentage. The measurement scale is given in “[]”.

other indices control for that. Reading performance was explained at an R^2 of 0.25. The model’s primary pathways are depicted in Fig. 4. As anticipated, lower inattention and better self-regulation, good family relations, perceived safety, and lower cotinine were associated with better reading performance in terms of total effects. Furthermore, girls, native German speakers, children having mothers with higher level of education, and those residing in North Tyrol demonstrated superior

reading performance. However, German tongue had a negative indirect effect on reading. Contrary to the theoretical expectations, a higher residential built environment score was associated with better reading, and the presence of a domestic garden was associated with poorer reading. Although, domestic gardens exhibited a modest positive indirect effect on reading mostly via lower cotinine, despite the absence of strong constituent pathways. Conversely, school nature exposure was found to be associated with better reading in line with theory. Table 2 shows a summary of the total, direct, and indirect effects on reading.

The multi-group SEM converged in 120 iterations and also fit the data well: $\chi^2(238) = 420.54, p < 0.001$; CFI = 0.97; RMSEA = 0.04 (90 % CI: 0.03, 0.04), SRMR = 0.04; and PNFI = 0.58). The results from the primary SEM held within the subgroup of children from North Tyrol (Supplementary Table S2). The precision of the effect estimates associated with all pathways was lower in the smaller group of children from South Tyrol where neither the built environment nor the natural environment exhibited significant total or indirect effects on reading. Additionally, German tongue was associated with reading only in North Tyrol, again positively in terms of total effect and negatively in terms of indirect effect. Though it was associated with a wide 95 % CI, it is noteworthy that the built environment had a negative effect on reading in South Tyrol. The effects of inattention, maternal education, male sex, and cotinine observed in the main SEM persisted across subgroups.

4. Discussion

4.1. General overview of results

The present study sought to investigate the associations between various components of the physical and social environments and reading performance of 3rd and 4th grade schoolchildren. The findings suggest that more positive family relations, better self-regulation, higher maternal education, female sex, lower cotinine, and greater level of natural land use around the school building were protectively associated with reading. These associations were found to be mediated by a combination of factors, including lower inattention and higher perceived safety of the neighborhood. Being a native German speaker and residence in North Tyrol also correlated with better reading performance. It is noteworthy that exposure to the built environment and the absence of a domestic garden were associated with better reading performance. A subsequent analysis, in which the data were stratified by Tyrol region, revealed variations in these association patterns between the north Austrian and the south Italian parts. These variations may offer a potential explanation for the unexpected observations.

The **inattention** score was directly associated with poorer reading and also functioned as an important mediator for other predictors of reading. This finding aligns with a prevailing consensus in the academic literature, which posits that reading difficulties or dyslexia frequently co-occur with other developmental conditions (Carroll et al., 2025; Ciulkinyte et al., 2025). A robust body of research has identified a particularly strong association with ADHD (Ciulkinyte et al., 2025), where inattention has been found as a pivotal predictor of dyslexia. Nevertheless, evidence suggests that the two conditions may also be concurrent and be explained by underlying transdiagnostic factors common to neurodevelopmental disorders (Kouki et al., 2025). We observed that **self-regulation** was predictive of better reading indirectly via lower inattention. According to the Active View of Reading Model, active self-regulation was expected to be central to managing the reading process (Duke and Cartwright, 2021). Self-regulated learners exhibit better comprehension due to their ability to set goals, monitor progress, and adjust strategies during reading (Lin et al., 2016; Cameron et al., 2024). Even on a daily basis, higher self-regulation is associated with higher academic success (Blume et al., 2022).

Better self-regulation at school was observed with higher levels of **naturalness**. The absence of an overall indirect effect of school nature on reading could be attributed to the presence of multiple competitive

Fig. 3. Polychoric correlations between the main variables in the study. Note. The intensity of the color scale corresponds to the strength of the correlation, with the red spectrum representing positive, and the blue spectrum negative correlations. L_{den} – address day-evening-night sound level from all traffic sources in dB, NO_2 – annual mean nitrogen dioxide level in $\mu g/m^3$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Path diagram illustrating the pathways linking physical, social, and perceptual characteristics of the home and school environments to children’s reading performance within the structural equation model (N = 1251). Note. Effect estimates shown are standardized beta coefficients from DWLS estimation regressions with their 95 % confidence interval (CI). The percentage values indicate the variance explained in the respective variable. Predictors of the physical exposure variables and coefficients with a p-value of >0.10 and paths for which clear a priori directional assumptions were not made are not shown to enhance clarity. Some variables appear multiple times in the figure only for presentational clarity. The simplified and full path diagrams with structural and measurement relationships are reported in [Supplementary Figs. S3 and S4](#).

pathways that act in a opposite directions and offset each other. Therefore, in contrast to the pathway through self-regulation and reduced inattention, which resulted in better reading performance, the school environment was associated with a more unfavorable perception of neighborhood quality and safety. In contrast to the observed relationship between perceived traffic safety on the way to school and reading performance, there was no evidence of a direct or indirect effect of perceived neighborhood quality on reading outcomes. This is another instance, where it is challenging to provide a comprehensive explanation, particularly when considering the results of previous analyses in this population on other outcomes (Lercher et al., 2025). In a previous study, Lercher et al. (2025) found that both neighborhood quality and safety perceptions contributed to better mental well-being in these children.

The **built environment** factor, which included indicators of traffic-related air and noise pollution and impervious land cover, demonstrated a total effect in an unlikely direction. One potential explanation could be that more built-up areas and closer proximity to traffic lines are spatially associated with higher maternal education in South Tyrol. In rural areas, families with higher education levels predominantly reside in the built-up center of the village due to proximity to services, schools, and transportation links, while farming parents with lower education levels primarily inhabit the outskirts in more green areas. This pattern was not observed in North Tyrol. This phenomenon may also offer a partial explanation for the protective association between residing in the northern regions and reading, as well as the association between being native German speaker and reading only in the North Tyrol. In the bilingual South Tyrol in Italy, children learn and speak two languages in

Table 2

Estimated total and indirect effects from the structural equation model linking physical, social, and perceptual characteristics of the home and school environments to children's reading performance (N = 1251).

Predictors	Total effects		Indirect effects	
	Estimate	95 % CI	Estimate	95 % CI
Male sex	-0.14	(-0.19, -0.08)	-0.04	(-0.06, -0.01)
German tongue	0.13	(0.06, 0.21)	-0.17	(-0.30, -0.05)
Maternal education	0.13	(0.06, 0.18)	0.02	(-0.02, 0.06)
Good family relations	0.12	(0.06, 0.18)	0.06	(0.03, 0.08)
North Tyrol	0.12	(0.07, 0.18)	-0.03	(-0.08, 0.02)
Built environment	0.63	(0.26, 1.00)	0.01	(-0.13, 0.14)
Domestic garden	-0.11	(-0.18, -0.03)	0.04	(0.01, 0.06)
School nature	0.34	(0.18, 0.50)	0.01	(-0.05, 0.07)
Cotinine	-0.07	(-0.12, -0.02)	-0.02	(-0.04, 0.003)
Perceived neighborhood quality	0.06	(-0.02, 0.13)	0.01	(-0.01, 0.04)
Perceived safety	0.09	(0.04, 0.15)	0.02	(-0.003, 0.04)
Poor self-regulation	-0.06	(-0.11, -0.002)	-0.10	(-0.13, -0.07)
Noise sensitivity	-0.02	(-0.08, 0.04)	-0.02	(-0.04, 0.01)
Inattention	-0.42	(-0.51, -0.34)	-	-

Note. Effect estimates shown are standardized beta coefficients from DWLS estimation regressions with their 95 % confidence interval (CI).

school. In contrast, in North Tyrol, a not being native German speaker is often indicative of a migration background, which is strongly associated with poorer reading skills (Wang, 2021). However, a comparative analysis reveals that Italian children demonstrated lower mean reading scores. This finding can be interpreted in the context of the disparate schooling systems in Austria and Italy. In Austria, children with significant disabilities are enrolled in specialized schools (Sonderschule), while Italy introduced an inclusive educational system in 1977. The majority of children (with regional variations) are integrated into regular classrooms and receive supplementary support from a teaching assistant. It is evident that this may have had a significant impact on the mean reading scores that were measured in regular schools. This observation is consistent with the findings of the study. Nonetheless, a 2006 PIRLS report indicates that Italian children demonstrate higher average scores than their Austrian counterparts (Kennedy et al., 2007). However, PISA 2006 indicated that a fifth of Austrian and a quarter of Italian students scored at or below Level 1 (OECD, 2008). More recently, the PISA study indicated that Austria and Italy experienced a decline in adult reading performance over the last 20 years, but the trend in Italy fluctuated over the years (OECD, 2023). Therefore, the picture seems more complex and beyond any simple explanation.

A positive correlation was identified between **school nature** and reading performance. A study conducted in Barcelona observed stronger associations between school greenness and children's progress in working memory and reduction in inattentiveness than for commuting or residential greenness (Dadvand et al., 2015). Although other studies did not specifically address reading skills, our observations appear to be consistent with the findings of studies that demonstrated that residing in a greener neighborhood and higher levels of greenness surrounding the school can facilitate normal behavioral development (Amoly et al., 2014), cognition (Buczylowska et al., 2023) and academic performance (Browning and Rigolon, 2019). In addition to the displacement of traffic infrastructure, which has been demonstrated to have an adverse

relationship with cognition and academic performance due to air pollution and noise emissions (Roche et al., 2024), natural school surroundings have been shown to be conducive to outdoor physical activity and play (Dzhambov et al., 2023; Roche et al., 2024). A substantial body of research has demonstrated that physical activity can have a positive impact on the mental well-being and academic performance of school-aged children (Lubans et al., 2016; Biddle et al., 2019). For instance, an analysis of 31 studies on children aged 6–12 years revealed that even a single instance of physical activity was associated with enhanced attention, while regular physical activity was associated with improved executive functions, attention, and academic achievement (de Greeff et al., 2018). Furthermore, spending class periods in natural environments has been demonstrated to engender a sense of communal cohesion among children. This can facilitate the development of social support systems and the cultivation of resilience resources through affiliative and cooperative play activities. These play activities have been shown to promote communication, mutual trust, and emotion regulation skills among children (Fabes et al., 2012; LaFreniere, 2013; Bakir-Demir et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2025). Even brief periods of nature exposure can be effective in reducing stress, restoring from attentional fatigue, and supporting restoration of relational resources among family members (Hartig, 2021). Drawing on the extant literature on the broader benefits of landscape diversity, we speculate that features such as species richness (Methorst, 2024), restorative natural soundscapes (Buxton et al., 2021), and human microbiota (Zhang et al., 2024) may have contributed to the positive association with reading.

Despite the observed correlation between school nature and **domestic gardens**, the functional similarities between school and home environments were not necessarily congruent. Many rural houses might not have a garden but are still surrounded by grasslands or forests. Furthermore, across the rural study area, the presence of gardens, which were private green spaces in this study context, is not necessarily indicative of economic prosperity. The correlation between maternal education and domestic gardens, as well as school nature, was found to be negative, which may have obscured the observed associations. However, gardens were found to be associated with lower exposure to secondhand smoke, which, in turn, was associated with better reading performance. This is consistent with slowly growing evidence supporting the positive impact of residential greenspace on substance use (Martin et al., 2020; Dzhambov et al., 2022; Wiley et al., 2022), where secondhand smoke is shown to undermine cognitive abilities and leaning (Fuemmeler et al., 2023). Still, we should be mindful that others have observed that passive smoking may serve as another proxy for socioeconomic status (Thiering et al., 2016).

The physical environment did not influence reading performance independently, rather in parallel with social factors, such as parent-child relations and maternal education. These family factors have been reported to affect children's reading ability via several mechanisms (Xu, 2023). For example, parents with a higher socioeconomic status may be more likely to read, to encourage positive engagement with reading, and foster interest and positive attitude toward reading and literacy in general. This contributes to a supportive learning environment. Furthermore, children to mothers with higher education have better self-regulation (Duyile et al., 2025). In Austria, children to mothers with completed tertiary education during the study period scored higher than those with lower education; students with an immigrant background who speak a non-German language at home scored lower than their counterparts (OECD, 2008). Additionally, positive family relationships create a buffer against stress, providing children with more social resources to cope with life's challenges and frustrations (Moschko et al., 2022). Our analysis suggested that good family relationships may indirectly impact reading by improving self-regulation and reducing inattention. Supportive, caring, and warm parenting creates a sense of security, stimulates the development of prosocial skills, and develops self-regulation abilities in children (Chen et al., 2022). For instance, a study of schoolchildren found that self-regulation changes over time

depended on the quality of parent-child interactions in everyday life (Moschko et al., 2022). Self-regulation may also differ between boys and girls across childhood (Coyné et al., 2015).

Taken together, the findings of this study suggest that examining the effects of individual factors offers limited mechanistic insights for prevention. However, few multi-exposure studies with adequate control for variable inclusion or pathway testing are available for language- or development-related outcomes, and the results are inconsistent (Jarvis et al., 2021; Garkov et al., 2024; Shoari et al., 2025; Yu et al., 2025). This makes it difficult to understand the various pathways and judge the potential for prevention and planning in schools and society (Costa et al., 2024; Roche et al., 2024). The null or counterintuitive findings of some studies can be due to insufficient control for and understanding of the cultural and geographic characteristics of the area. The social exposome is a useful framework for understanding how the physical and social environments jointly affect outcomes such as reading (Gudi-Mindermann et al., 2023). Another proposition supported by the results is that child perceptions, reflecting internalized information on environmental characteristics and cognitive representations of them, can reveal meaningful pathways of influence as illustrated in the present study. Children can form abstract ideas about how environmental factors affect their health, which can inform local decision-making processes (Shortt and Ross, 2021). Other avenues of prevention may focus on integrating self-regulation teaching into the regular school curriculum (Schunk et al., 2022).

One important aspect that remains untapped by our study is the role of the digital environment that nowadays takes up a considerable amount of children's time (Li et al., 2024) and often reduces academic performance (Adelantado-Renau et al., 2019). Spending time on social media or in front of a screen in general competes for time with outdoor activities (Larson et al., 2019) that children today engage in less than back in 2004–2005 when the data for the current study were collected. However, digital environments are not necessarily detrimental to cognition and academic outcomes (Silva et al., 2025). Opportunities for virtual contact with nature can also have restorative effects on students (Shin et al., 2022) or may even enhance nature experiences for those challenged by disability or other circumstances to physically access nature (Owens and Bunce, 2023).

4.2. Strengths and limitations

The objective of this study was to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by investigating multiple exposures that reflect aspects of the physical and social exposomes, as well as child perceptions. The extent to which participants were exposed to nature was measured in two distinct environments: their homes and their school surroundings. In addition, the study was conducted in an area with low level of urbanization, which is rarely seen in the literature. The survey captured data from 85 % of the local schools, which were selected at random within the study area, thereby enhancing the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, the utilization of multiple information sources (i.e., children, mothers, and teachers) has arguably reduced common method bias associated with relying on a single informant for all variables included in a causal pathway analysis. On the other hand, having different sources of data may have attenuated the associations between the respective variables. For example, parents and teachers may be aware only of salient behaviors of the children or incorporate own subjective perceptions in their reports, while children may not consider all relevant features of their surrounding environment.

The study was constrained by a number of other features. With a cross-sectional design we could not establish direct cause-and-effect relationships. For example, we specified a path from self-regulation to inattention but we recognize that these measures may belong to a higher order latent factor representing a broader dimension of individual behavioral functioning. Another limitation was that reliable traffic emissions data were not available for the schools. Actual biodiversity

indicators were also unavailable and land use diversity was a crude proxy for it. We acknowledge that the conceptual model that was tested could have been enriched with additional exposures and mediators. However, data for many of those were unavailable. For instance, we were unable to account for intrauterine exposure to neurotoxic chemicals or stressors, and we decided against including smoking during pregnancy in the model because of its strong associations with cotinine. In addition, the domestic learning environment and family reading practices were not measured. It would be worthwhile investigating the interaction of prenatal and early-life exposures in future research. Next, some unmeasured factors have only emerged to prominence in the decades that followed the data collection for our study, owing to the profound cultural and technological changes resulting in the widespread adoption of social media platforms and personal electronic devices. In our dataset we had a measure of media use but due to the low level of media exposure at that time and the non-existence of social media, it was not used in the analyses. Thus, our findings paint a limited picture of the information overload and screen time challenges faced by modern children. Finally, the model's goodness-of-fit indices should be interpreted with some caution because under the DWLS estimator the conventional cut-offs for some of them tend to bias towards a better fit (Groskurth et al., 2024).

5. Conclusions

Reading performance in Austrian and Italian children was associated with the intertwined physical and social aspects of their school and home environments. These relationships appeared to be influenced by children's perceptions of their living context, which should be considered when designing environments that support cognitive development and academic performance. Examining the effects of individual factors offers limited mechanistic insights for prevention of mitigation of reading difficulties. Understanding local socioeconomic, land use, and cultural patterns across geographies can help better explain the complex associations between environments and children's reading performance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Angel M. Dzhambov: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Peter Lercher:** Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jan Spilski:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Johannes Rüdiger:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Matthew H.E.M. Browning:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Iana Markevych:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work the authors used DeepL in order to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2025.114683>.

References

- Adelantado-Renau, M., Moliner-Urdiales, D., Cavero-Redondo, I., Beltran-Valls, M.R., Martínez-Vizcaíno, V., Álvarez-Bueno, C., 2019. Association between screen media use and academic performance among children and adolescents: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Pediatr.* 173 (11), 1058–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2019.3176>.
- American Psychiatric Association, 2013. *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, fifth ed.* American Psychiatric Association, Washington, DC.
- Amoly, E., Dadvand, P., Forns, J., López-Vicente, M., Basagaña, X., Julvez, J., Alvarez-Pedrerol, M., Nieuwenhuijsen, M.J., Sunyer, J., 2014. Green and blue spaces and behavioral development in Barcelona schoolchildren: the BREATHE project. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 122 (12), 1351–1358. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1408215>.
- Amrhein, V., Greenland, S., McShane, B., 2019. Scientists rise up against statistical significance. *Nature* 567 (7748), 305–307. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-00857-9>.
- Andreola, C., Mascheretti, S., Belotti, R., Ogliari, A., Marino, C., Battaglia, M., Scaini, S., 2021. The heritability of reading and reading-related neurocognitive components: a multi-level meta-analysis. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* 121, 175–200.
- Bakir-Demir, T., Berument, S.K., Sahin-Acar, B., 2019. The relationship between greenery and self-regulation of children: the mediation role of nature connectedness. *J. Environ. Psychol.* 65, 101327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2019.101327>.
- Basu, S., Banerjee, B., 2020. Impact of environmental factors on mental health of children and adolescents: a systematic review. *Child. Youth Serv. Rev.* 119, 105515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105515>.
- Berto, R., Pasini, M., Barbiero, G., 2015. How does psychological restoration work in children? An exploratory study. *J. Child Adolesc. Behav.* 3, 200. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2375-4494.1000200>.
- Biddle, S.J.H., Ciacconi, S., Thomas, G., Vergeer, I., 2019. Physical activity and mental health in children and adolescents: an updated review of reviews and an analysis of causality. *Psychol. Sport Exerc.* 42, 146–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2018.08.011>.
- Blume, F., Imer, A., Dirk, J., Schmiedek, F., 2022. Day-to-day variation in students' academic success: the role of self-regulation, working memory, and achievement goals. *Dev. Sci.* 25 (6), e13301. <https://doi.org/10.1111/desc.13301>.
- Boeniger, M.F., Lowry, L.K., Rosenberg, J., 1993. Interpretation of urine results used to assess chemical exposure with emphasis on creatinine adjustments: a review. *Am. Ind. Hyg. Assoc. J.* 54 (10), 615–627. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15298669391355134>.
- Boman, B., 2022. Regional differences in educational achievement: a replication study of municipality data. *Front. Educ.* 7, 854342. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.854342>.
- Boyaci, H., Etiler, N., Duman, C., Basyigit, I., Pala, A., 2006. Environmental tobacco smoke exposure in school children: parent report and urine cotinine measures. *Pediatr. Int.* 48 (4), 382–389. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1442-200X.2006.02225.x>.
- Broer, M., Bai, Y., Fonseca, F., 2019. A review of the literature on socioeconomic status and educational achievement. In: Broer, M., Bai, Y., Fonseca, F. (Eds.), *Socioeconomic Inequality and Educational Outcomes: Evidence from Twenty Years of TIMSS*. Springer International Publishing, pp. 7–17. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11991-1_2.
- Bronfenbrenner, U., Morris, P.A., 1998. The ecology of developmental processes. In: Damon, W., Lerner, R.M. (Eds.), *Handbook of Child Psychology: Theoretical Models of Human Development, fifth ed.* John Wiley & Sons, Inc, pp. 993–1028.
- Browning, M.H.E.M., Rigolon, A., 2019. School green space and its impact on academic performance: a systematic literature review. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Publ. Health* 16 (3), 429. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16030429>.
- Buckingham, J., Wheldall, K., Beaman-Wheldall, R., 2013. Why poor children are more likely to become poor readers: the school years. *Aust. J. Educ.* 57 (3), 190–213.
- Buczylowska, D., Zhao, T., Singh, N., Jurczak, A., Siry, A., Markevych, I., 2023. Exposure to greenspace and bluespace and cognitive functioning in children - a systematic review. *Environ. Res.* 222, 115340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.115340>.
- Burgess, S.R., Hecht, S.A., Lonigan, C.J., 2002. Relations of the home literacy environment (HLE) to the development of reading-related abilities: a one-year longitudinal study. *Read. Res. Q.* 37 (4), 408–426.
- Buxton, R.T., Pearson, A.L., Allou, C., Fristrup, K., Wittemyer, G., 2021. A synthesis of health benefits of natural sounds and their distribution in national parks. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 118 (14), e2013097118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2013097118>.
- Cameron, C.E., McClelland, M.M., Grammer, J., Morrison, F.J., 2024. Self-regulation and academic achievement. In: Bell, M.A. (Ed.), *Child Development at the Intersection of Emotion and Cognition*, second ed. American Psychological Association, pp. 213–234. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0000406-011>.
- Carroll, J.M., Holden, C., Kirby, P., Thompson, P.A., Snowling, M.J., Dyslexia, Delphi Panel, et al., 2025. Toward a consensus on dyslexia: findings from a Delphi study. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.14123>.
- Carroll, J.M., Maughan, B., Goodman, R., Meltzer, H., 2005. Literacy difficulties and psychiatric disorders: evidence for comorbidity. *J. Child Psychol. Psychiatr.* 46, 524–532.
- Chen, J., Hu, Z., Lu, A., Ma, T., 2022. How do family factors impact children's emotional regulation? <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.220704.049>.
- Chen, R., Clifford, A., Lang, L., Anstey, K.J., 2013. Is exposure to secondhand smoke associated with cognitive parameters of children and adolescents? a systematic literature review. *Ann. Epidemiol.* 23 (10), 652–661.
- Ciulkinyte, A., Mountford, H.S., Fontanillas, P., et al., 2025. Genetic neurodevelopmental clustering and dyslexia. *Mol. Psychiatr.* 30 (140), 150. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41380-024-02649-8>.
- Claesen, J.L., Wheeler, A.J., Kladders, G., Gonzalez, D.D., Molina, M.A., Tham, R., et al., 2021. Associations of traffic-related air pollution and greenery with academic outcomes among primary schoolchildren. *Environ. Res.* 199, 111325.
- Costa, A., Moreira, D., Casanova, J., Azevedo, A., Gonçalves, A., Oliveira, Í., et al., 2024. Determinants of academic achievement from the middle to secondary school education: a systematic review. *Soc. Psychol. Educ.* 27 (6), 3533–3572.
- Côté-Lussier, C., Jackson, J., Kestens, Y., Henderson, M., Barnett, T.A., 2015. A child's view: social and physical environmental features differentially predict parent and child perceived neighborhood safety. *J. Urban Health* 92 (1), 10–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-014-9917-0>.
- Coyne, M.A., Vaske, J.C., Boisvert, D.L., et al., 2015. Sex differences in the stability of self-regulation across childhood. *J. Dev. Life Course Criminol.* 1, 4–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40865-015-0001-6>.
- Dadvand, P., Nieuwenhuijsen, M.J., Esnaola, M., Forns, J., Basagaña, X., Alvarez-Pedrerol, M., Rivas, I., López-Vicente, M., De Castro Pascual, M., Su, J., Jerrett, M., Querol, X., Sunyer, J., 2015. Green spaces and cognitive development in primary schoolchildren. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 112 (26), 7937–7942. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1503402112>.
- Daniel, S.S., et al., 2006. Suicidality, school dropout, and reading problems among adolescents. *J. Learn. Disabil.* 39, 507–514.
- de Greeff, J.W., Bosker, R.J., Oosterlaan, J., Visscher, C., Hartman, E., 2018. Effects of physical activity on executive functions, attention and academic performance in preadolescent children: a meta-analysis. *J. Sci. Med. Sport* 21 (5), 501–507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2017.09.595>.
- DeFries, J.C., Gillis, J.J., 1993. Genetics of reading disability. In: Plomin, R., McClearn, G.E. (Eds.), *Nature, Nurture & Psychology*. American Psychological Association, pp. 121–145. <https://doi.org/10.1037/10131-006>.
- DiStefano, C., Morgan, G.B., 2014. A comparison of diagonal weighted least squares robust estimation techniques for ordinal data. *Struct. Equ. Model: A Multidiscip. J.* 21 (3), 425–438. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705511.2014.915373>.
- Duke, N.K., Cartwright, K.B., 2021. The science of reading progresses: communicating advances beyond the simple view of reading. *Read. Res. Q.* 56 (Suppl. 1), S25–S44. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rq.411>.
- Duncan, G.J., Dowsett, C.J., Claessens, A., Magnuson, K., Huston, A.C., Klebanov, P., Pagani, L.S., Feinstein, L., Engel, M., Brooks-Gunn, J., Sexton, H., Duckworth, K., Japel, C., 2007. School readiness and later achievement. *Dev. Psychol.* 43 (6), 1428–1446. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.43.6.1428>.
- DuPaul, G.J., Morgan, P.L., Farkas, G., Hillemeier, M.M., Maczuga, S., 2016. Academic and social functioning associated with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder: latent class analyses of trajectories from kindergarten to fifth grade. *J. Abnorm. Child Psychol.* 44, 1425–1438.
- Duyile, B.E., LoCasale-Crouch, J., NeSmith, T.B., Turnbull, K.L.P., Colson, E., Corwin, M.J., Mateus, M.C., Forbes, E., Geller, N., Heeren, T., Hauck, F.R., Jaworski, B., Kellams, A., Kerr, S., Moon, R.Y., 2025. Maternal education and child self-regulation: do maternal self-regulation and responsiveness mediate the association? *Acad. Pediatr.* 25 (1), 102484. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2024.03.012>.
- Dzhambov, A.M., Lercher, P., Rüdiger, J., Browning, M.H.E.M., Markevych, I., 2022. Home gardens and distances to nature associated with behavior problems in alpine schoolchildren: role of secondhand smoke exposure and biomarkers. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 243, 113975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2022.113975>.
- Dzhambov, A.M., Markevych, I., Lercher, P., 2019. Associations of residential greenness, traffic noise, and air pollution with birth outcomes across alpine areas. *Sci. Total Environ.* 678, 399–408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.05.019>.
- Dzhambov, A.M., Lercher, P., Vincens, N., Persson, P., Klatte, M., Leist, L., Lachmann, T., Schreckenber, D., Belke, C., Ristovska, G., Kanninen, K.M., Botteldooren, D., Van Renterghem, T., Jeram, S., Selander, J., Arat, A., White, K., Julvez, J., Clark, C., Foraster, M., et al., 2023. Protective effect of restorative possibilities on cognitive function and mental health in children and adolescents: a scoping review including the role of physical activity. *Environ. Res.* 233, 116452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116452>.

- Elliott, J.G., Grigorenko, E.L., 2024. Dyslexia in the twenty-first century: a commentary on the IDA definition of dyslexia. *Ann. Dyslexia* 74 (3), 363–377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11881-024-00311-0>.
- Erbeli, F., Rice, M., Paracchini, S., 2021. Insights into dyslexia genetics research from the last two decades. *Brain Sci.* 12 (1), 27.
- Evans, G.W., Schamberg, M.A., 2009. Childhood poverty, chronic stress, and adult working memory. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 106 (16), 6545–6549. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0811910106>.
- Fabes, R.A., Hanish, L.D., Martin, C.L., Moss, A., Reising, A., 2012. The effects of young children's affiliations with prosocial peers on subsequent emotionality in peer interactions. *Br. J. Dev. Psychol.* 30 (Pt 4), 569–585. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-835X.2011.02073.x>.
- Fuemmeler, B.F., Glasgow, T.E., Schechter, J.C., Maguire, R., Sheng, Y., Bidopia, T., Barsell, D.J., Ksinan, A., Zhang, J., Lin, Y., Hoyo, C., Murphy, S., Qin, J., Wang, X., Kollins, S., 2023. Prenatal and childhood smoke exposure associations with cognition, language, and Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity disorder. *J. Pediatr.* 256, 77–84.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2022.11.041>.
- Gardi, C., Bosco, C., Rusco, E., Montanarella, L., 2010. An analysis of the Land Use Sustainability Index (LUSI) at territorial scale based on Corine Land Cover. *Manag. Environ. Qual. Int. J.* 21 (5), 680–694.
- Garkov, S., Dearden, L., Armstrong, B., Milojevic, A., 2024. The relationship between PM2.5, greenness, and road noise exposures and children's cognitive performance in England: the millennium cohort Study. *Environments* 11 (10), 213. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos15101197>.
- Gheller, F., Spicciarelli, G., Scimemi, P., Arfé, B., 2023. The effects of noise on children's cognitive performance: a systematic review. *Environ. Behav.* 55 (8–10), 698–734.
- Grineski, S.E., Collins, T.W., Adkins, D.E., 2020. Hazardous air pollutants are associated with worse performance in reading, math, and science among US primary schoolchildren. *Environ. Res.* 181, 108925.
- Groskurth, K., Bluemke, M., Lechner, C.M., 2024. Why we need to abandon fixed cutoffs for goodness-of-fit indices: an extensive simulation and possible solutions. *Behav. Res.* 56, 3891–3914. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-023-02193-3>.
- Gudi-Mindermann, H., White, M., Roczen, J., Riedel, N., Dreger, S., Bolte, G., 2023. Integrating the social environment with an equity perspective into the exposome paradigm: a new conceptual framework of the social exposome. *Environ. Res.* 233, 116485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116485>.
- Harris, E.L., 1982. Genetic and environmental influences on reading achievement: a study of first- and second-grade twin children. *Acta Genet. Med. Gemellol.: Twin Res.* 31 (1–2), 64–116.
- Hart, S.A., Petrill, S.A., Willcutt, E., Thompson, L.A., Schatschneider, C., Deater-Deckard, K., Cutting, L.E., 2010. Exploring how symptoms of attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder are related to reading and mathematics performance: general genes, general environments. *Psychol. Sci.* 21 (11), 1708–1715.
- Hartig, T., 2021. Restoration in nature: beyond the conventional narrative. In: Schutte, A.R., Torquati, J.C., Stevens, J.R. (Eds.), *Nature and Psychology: Biological, Cognitive, Developmental, and Social Pathways to well-being*. Springer, Nature Switzerland AG, pp. 89–151. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-69020-5_5.
- Haufroid, V., Lison, D., 1998. Urinary cotinine as a tobacco-smoke exposure index: a minireview. *Int. Arch. Occup. Environ. Health* 71 (3), 162–168. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004200050266>.
- Hayball, F., McCrorie, P., Kirk, A., Gibson, A.M., Ellaway, A., 2018. Exploring children's perceptions of their local environment in relation to time spent outside. *Child. Soc.* 32 (1), 14–26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12217>.
- Heinonen-Guzejev, M., 2009. Noise sensitivity – medical, psychological and genetic aspects [Ph.D. thesis]. University of Helsinki.
- Hill, E.M., 2012. Noise sensitivity and diminished health: the role of stress-related factors [Ph.D. thesis]. Auckland University of Technology.
- Hu, L., Bentler, P.M., 1999. Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Struct. Equ. Model.: A Multidiscip. J.* 6 (1), 1–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>.
- Iacobucci, D., 2010. Structural equations modeling: Fit indices, sample size, and advanced topics. *J. Consum. Psychol.* 20 (1), 90–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2009.09.003>.
- Infantino, E., Barnett, T.A., Côté-Lussier, C., et al., 2024. Feeling safe: a critical look at the effect of neighborhood safety features and perceptions on childhood symptoms of depression. *BMC Pediatr.* 24, 774. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-024-05236-6>.
- Jarvis, I., Davis, Z., Sbihi, H., Brauer, M., Czekajlo, A., Davies, H.W., Gergel, S.E., Guhn, M., Jerrett, M., Koehoorn, M., et al., 2021. Assessing the association between lifetime exposure to greenspace and early childhood development and the mediation effects of air pollution and noise in Canada: a population-based birth cohort study. *Lancet Planet. Health* 5, e709–e717.
- Kennedy, A.M., Mullis, I.V., Martin, M.O., Trong, K.L., 2007. PIRLS 2006 Encyclopedia: a Guide to Reading Education in the Forty PIRLS 2006 Countries. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement, Herengracht 487, Amsterdam, 1017 BT, The Netherlands.
- Klatte, M., Bergström, K., Lachmann, T., 2013. Does noise affect learning? A short review on noise effects on cognitive performance in children. *Front. Psychol.* 4, 578. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00578>.
- Klatte, M., Spilski, J., Mayerl, J., Möhler, U., Lachmann, T., Bergström, K., 2017. Effects of aircraft noise on reading and quality of life in primary school children in Germany: results from the NORAH study. *Environ. Behav.* 49 (4), 390–424. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916516642580>.
- Kouki, E.-P., Tsagaraki, A., Spanoudis, G.C., Papadopoulos, T.C., 2025. "Single Deficit, Comorbidity or Varying Degrees of Dysfunction? New Directions to the Study of Learning Disorders." *Appl. Cogn. Psychol.* 39 (4), e70078. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.70078>.
- Kuo, M., Browning, M.H.E.M., Sachdeva, S., Lee, K., Westphal, L., 2018. Might school performance grow on trees? Examining the link between "Greenness" and academic achievement in urban, high-poverty schools. *Front. Psychol.* 9, 1669. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01669>.
- Küspert, P., Schneider, W., 1998. Würzburger Leise Leseprobe (WLLP). Hogrefe, Göttingen.
- Kweon, B.S., Ellis, C.D., Lee, J., Jacobs, K., 2017. The link between school environments and student academic performance. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 23, 35–43.
- LaFreniere, P., 2013. Children's play as a context for managing physiological arousal and learning emotion regulation. *Psychologjiske Teme* 22 (2), 183–204.
- Langley, M.D., Van Houghton, K., McBeath, M.K., Lucca, K., 2023. Children and adults exhibit a common vertical attention bias for object tops and scene bottoms. *Dev. Psychol.* 59 (8), 1377–1388. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001553>.
- Larson, L.R., Szczytko, R., Bowers, E.P., Stephens, L.E., Stevenson, K.T., Floyd, M.F., 2019. Outdoor time, screen time, and connection to nature: troubling trends among rural youth? *Environ. Behav.* 51 (8), 966–991. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916518806686>.
- Lercher, P., Dzhambov, A.M., Persson Waye, K., 2025. Environmental perceptions, self-regulation, and coping with noise mediate the associations between children's physical environment and sleep and mental health problems. *Environ. Res.* 264 (Pt 2), 120414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2024.120414>.
- Li, M., Zhao, R., Dang, X., Xu, X., Chen, R., Chen, Y., Zhang, Y., Zhao, Z., Wu, D., 2024. Causal relationships between screen use, reading, and brain development in early adolescents. *Adv. Sci. (Weinh.)* 11 (11), e2307540. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.202307540>.
- Lin, B., Coburn, S.S., Eisenberg, N., 2016. Self-regulation and reading achievement. In: McDonald Connor C. *The Cognitive Development of Reading and Reading Comprehension*, pp. 67–86.
- Ling, J., Heffernan, T., 2016. The cognitive deficits associated with second-hand smoking. *Front. Psychiatr.* 7, 46. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00046>.
- Liu, D., 2024. Cross-national analysis of differences in student reading performance: taking PISA 2022 as an example. *Lecture Notes Edu. Psychol. Public Media* 54, 37–43.
- Lubans, D., Richards, J., Hillman, C., Faulkner, G., Beauchamp, M., Nilsson, M., Kelly, P., Smith, J., Raine, L., Biddle, S., 2016. Physical activity for cognitive and mental health in youth: a systematic review of mechanisms. *Pediatrics* 138 (3), e20161642. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1642>.
- Manu, M., Torppa, M., Vasalampi, K., Lerkanen, M.K., Poikkeus, A.M., Niemi, P., 2023. Reading development from kindergarten to age 18: the role of gender and parental education. *Read. Res. Q.* 58 (4), 505–538.
- Marselle, M.R., Hartig, T., Cox, D.T.C., de Bell, S., Knapp, S., Lindley, S., Triguero-Mas, M., Böhning-Gaese, K., Braubach, M., Cook, P.A., de Vries, S., Heintz-Buschart, A., Hofmann, M., Irvine, K.N., Kabisch, N., Kolek, F., Kraemer, R., Markevych, I., Martens, D., Müller, R., Nieuwenhuijsen, M., Potts, J.M., Stadler, J., Walton, S., Warber, S.L., Bonn, A., 2021. Pathways linking biodiversity to human health: a conceptual framework. *Environ. Int.* 150, 106420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106420>.
- Martin, L., White, M.P., Pahl, S., May, J., Wheeler, B.W., 2020. Neighbourhood greenspace and smoking prevalence: results from a nationally representative survey in England. *Soc. Sci. Med.* 265, 113448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113448>, 1982.
- Mascheretti, S., Lampis, V., Andreola, C., Lecce, S., Dionne, G., 2024. Continuity and change of genetic and environmental influences on reading and reading-related neurocognitive skills: a systematic review of longitudinal twin studies. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* 159, 105576.
- Maughan, B., Carroll, J., 2006. Literacy and mental disorders. *Curr. Opin. Psychiatr.* 19, 350–354.
- Mayringer, H., Wimmer, H., 2003. Salzburger Lesescreening Für Die Klassenstufen 1-4 (SLS 1-4). Hans Huber.
- McDonald, S., Dowda, M., Colabianchi, N., Porter, D., Dishman, R.K., Pate, R.R., 2015. Perceptions of the neighborhood environment and children's afterschool moderate-to-vigorous physical activity. *Pediatr. Exerc. Sci.* 27 (2), 243–251. <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.2014-0139>.
- Mealings, K., 2022. Classroom acoustic conditions and primary school children's behaviour: a scoping review. *Build. Acoust.* 29 (4), 543–558.
- Meltzer, H., Vostanis, P., Goodman, R., Ford, T., 2007. Children's perceptions of neighbourhood trustworthiness and safety and their mental health. *J. Child Psychol. Psychiatr. Allied Discip.* 48 (12), 1208–1213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.2007.01800.x>.
- Methorst, J., 2024. Positive relationship between bird diversity and human mental health: an analysis of repeated cross-sectional data. *Lancet Planet. Health* 8 (5), e285–e296. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(24\)00023-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(24)00023-8).
- Milojevic, A., Dutey-Magni, P., Dearden, L., Wilkinson, P., 2021. Lifelong exposure to air pollution and cognitive development in young children: the UK millennium cohort study. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 16 (5), 055023.
- Moschko, T., Stadler, G., Gawrilow, C., 2022. Fluctuations in children's self-regulation and parent-child interaction in everyday life: an ambulatory assessment study. *J. Soc. Pers. Relat.* 40 (1), 254–276. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02654075221116788> (Original work published 2023).
- Mugnaini, D., Lassi, S., La Malfa, G., Albertini, G., 2009. Internalizing correlates of dyslexia. *World J. Clin. Pediatr.* 5, 255–264.
- Muscat, J.E., Liu, A., Richie Jr., J.P., 2011. A comparison of creatinine vs. specific gravity to correct for urinary dilution of cotinine. *Biomarkers* 16 (3), 206–211. <https://doi.org/10.3109/1354750X.2010.538084>.
- Needleman, H.L., Gunnoe, C., Leviton, A., Reed, R., Peresie, H., Maher, C., Barrett, P., 1979. Deficits in psychological and classroom performance of children with elevated

- dentine lead levels. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 300 (13), 689–695. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM197903293001301>.
- Nguyen, N., Fashing, P.J., Trosvik, P., et al., 2025. A quantitative comparison of patterns of play and conflict in nature preschool and traditional preschool children in Norway. *IJEC* 57, 181–207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-024-00394-1>.
- Niklas, F., Schneider, W., 2017. Home learning environment and development of child competencies from kindergarten until the end of elementary school. *Contemp. Educ. Psychol.* 49, 263–274.
- OECD, 2008. PISA 2006: Volume 2: Data, PISA. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264040151-en>. ISBN978-92-64-04014-4.
- OECD, 2023. PISA 2022 Results (Volume I): the State of Learning and Equity in Education, PISA. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/53f23881-en>. ISBN978-92-64-35128-8(pdf).
- OECD, 2024a. Survey of Adults Skills 2023: Austria. OECD Publishing, Paris. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/survey-of-adults-skills-2023-country-notes_ab4f6b8c-en/austria_19e61a75-en.html.
- OECD, 2024b. Survey of Adults Skills 2023: Italy. OECD Publishing, Paris. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/survey-of-adults-skills-2023-country-notes_ab4f6b8c-en/italy_b03d6066-en.html.
- Owens, M., Bunce, H., 2023. The effect of brief exposure to virtual nature on mental wellbeing in adolescents. *Sci. Rep.* 13, 17769. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-44717-z>.
- Park, H., 2008. Home literacy environments and children's reading performance: a comparative study of 25 countries. *Educ. Res. Eval.* 14 (6), 489–505.
- Persson Wayne, K., Löve, J., Lercher, P., Dzhambov, A.M., Klätte, M., Schreckenberger, D., Belke, C., Leist, L., Ristovska, G., Jeram, S., Kanninen, K.M., Selander, J., Arat, A., Lachmann, T., Clark, C., Botteldooren, D., White, K., Julvez, J., Foraster, M., Kaprio, J., Bolte, G., Psyllidis, A., Gulliver, J., Boshuizen, H., Bozzon, A., Fels, J., Hornikx, M., van den Hazel, P., Weber, M., Brambilla, M., Braat-Eggen, E., Van Kamp, I., Vincens, N., Equal-life Scientific Team, 2023. Adopting a child perspective for exposome research on mental health and cognitive development - conceptualisation and opportunities. *Environ. Res.* 239 (Pt 1), 117279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.117279>.
- R Core Team, 2024. R: a Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Ravens-Sieberer, U., Bullinger, M., 1998. Assessing health-related quality of life in chronically ill children with the German KINDL: first psychometric and content analytical results. *Qual. Life Res.* 7 (5), 399–407. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:100853819715>.
- Roche, I.V., Ubalde-Lopez, M., Daher, C., Nieuwenhuijsen, M., Gascon, M., 2024. The health-related and learning performance effects of air pollution and other urban-related environmental factors on school-age children and Adolescents-A scoping review of systematic reviews. *Curr. Environ. Health Rep.* 11 (2), 300–316. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-024-00431-0>.
- Rosseel, Y., 2012. Lavaan: an R package for structural equation modeling. *J. Stat. Software* 48 (2), 1–36. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v048.i02>.
- Sacco, C., Falzetti, P., 2021. Spatial variations of school-level determinants of reading achievement in Italy. *Large-scale Assessments Edu.* 9 (1), 12.
- Schunk, D., Berger, E.M., Hermes, H., Winkel, K., Fehr, E., 2022. Teaching self-regulation. *Nat. Hum. Behav.* 6 (12), 1680–1690. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-022-01449-w>.
- Shaywitz, S.E., Escobar, M.D., Shaywitz, B.A., Fletcher, J.M., Makuch, R., 1992. Evidence that dyslexia may represent the lower tail of a normal distribution of reading ability. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 326 (3), 145–150. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM199201163260301>.
- Shin, S., Browning, M.H., Dzhambov, A.M., 2022. Window access to nature restores: a virtual reality experiment with greenspace views, sounds, and smells. *Ecopsychology* 14 (4), 253–265. <https://doi.org/10.1089/eco.2021.0032>.
- Shoari, N., Blangiardo, M., Pirani, M., 2025. Neighborhood characteristics and mental health from childhood to adolescence. *JAMA Netw. Open* 8 (4), e254470.
- Shortt, N.K., Ross, C., 2021. Children's perceptions of environment and health in two Scottish neighbourhoods. *Soc. Sci. Med.* 283, 114186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114186>.
- Shulman, K., Baicker, K., Mayes, L., 2024. Reading for life-long health. *Front. Pediatr.* 12, 1401739. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2024.1401739>.
- Silva, K., Breeland, N., Clark, A.M., Öztekin, I., Kelly, R.L., 2025. Effects of virtual reality use in children aged 10 to 12 years. *Front. Virtual Real* 6, 1547198. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frvir.2025.1547198>.
- Sobel, M.E., 1982. Asymptotic confidence intervals for indirect effects in structural equation models. *Sociol. Methodol.* 13, 290–312.
- StataCorp, 2025. Stata Statistical Software: Release 19. StataCorp LLC, College Station, TX.
- Sunyer, J., Esnaola, M., Alvarez-Pedrerol, M., Forn, J., Rivas, I., López-Vicente, M., et al., 2015. Association between traffic-related air pollution in schools and cognitive development in primary school children: a prospective cohort study. *PLoS Med.* 12 (3), e1001792.
- Tangermann, L., Vienneau, D., Saucy, A., Hattendorf, J., Schäffer, B., Wunderli, J.M., Rösli, M., 2023. The association of road traffic noise with cognition in adolescents: a cohort study in Switzerland. *Environ. Res.* 218, 115031.
- Thiering, E., Markevych, I., Brüske, I., Fuertes, E., Kratzsch, J., Sugiri, D., Hoffmann, B., von Berg, A., Bauer, C.P., Koletzko, S., Berdel, D., Heinrich, J., 2016. Associations of residential long-term air pollution exposures and satellite-derived greenness with insulin resistance in German adolescents. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 124 (8), 1291–1298. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1509967>. Epub 2016 Feb 5. PMID: 26863688; PMCID: PMC4977044.
- Torppa, M., Vasalampi, K., Eklund, K., Niemi, P., 2022. Long-term effects of the home literacy environment on reading development: familial risk for dyslexia as a moderator. *J. Exp. Child Psychol.* 215, 105314.
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2017. More than one-half of Children and Adolescents are Not Learning Worldwide (Fact Sheet No. 46, UIS/FS/2017/ED/46). UNESCO. <https://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/fs46-more-than-half-children-not-learning-en-2017.pdf>.
- Ursache, A., Barajas-Gonzalez, R.G., Dawson-McClure, S., 2022. Neighborhood influences on the development of self-regulation among children of color living in historically disinvested neighborhoods: moderators and mediating mechanisms. *Front. Psychol.* 13, 953304. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.953304>.
- van Lier, L.E., Utter, J., Denny, S., Lucassen, M., Dyson, B., Clark, T., 2017. Home gardening and the health and well-being of adolescents. *Health Promot. Pract.* 18 (1), 34–43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524839916673606>. Epub 2016 Oct 22. PMID: 27765876.
- Voyer, D., Voyer, S.D., 2014. Gender differences in scholastic achievement: a meta-analysis. *Psychol. Bull.* 140 (4), 1174.
- Wang, Z., 2021. Mind the gap: examining migrant-native disparities in reading performance and subjective wellbeing among 15-year-old students in different education systems. *Int. J. Educ. Res. Open* 2, 100087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2021.100087>.
- Wasserstein, R.L., Lazar, N.A., 2016. The ASA's statement on p-values: context, process, and purpose. *Am. Statistician* 70 (2), 129–133. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2016.1154108>.
- Wasserstein, R.L., Schirm, A.L., Lazar, N.A., 2019. Moving to a world beyond "p < 0.05". *Am. Statistician* 73 (Suppl. 1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2019.1583913>.
- Wiley, E.R., Stranges, S., Gilliland, J.A., Anderson, K.K., Seabrook, J.A., 2022. Residential greenness and substance use among youth and young adults: associations with alcohol, tobacco, and marijuana use. *Environ. Res.* 212 (Pt A), 113124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.113124>.
- Xu, R., 2023. Family factors affecting children's reading ability. *Lecture Notes Edu. Psychol. Public Media* 6, 589–597.
- Yang, L., Li, C., Li, X., Zhai, M., An, Q., Zhang, Y., Zhao, J., Weng, X., 2022. Prevalence of developmental dyslexia in primary school children: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Brain Sci.* 12 (2), 240. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12020240>.
- Yolton, K., Dietrich, P., Auinger, D., Lanphear, B.P., Hornung, R., 2005. Exposure to environmental tobacco smoke and cognitive abilities among U.S. children and adolescents. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 113, 98–103. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.7210>.
- Yu, X., Jarvis, I., van den Bosch, M., Guhn, M., Sbihi, H., Davies, H., 2025. Residential exposure to noise, green space, and children's language acquisition. *Environ. Int.* 109524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109524>.
- Zhang, Y.D., Zhou, G.L., Wang, L., Browning, M.H.E.M., Markevych, I., Heinrich, J., Knibbs, L.D., Zhao, T., Ding, Y., Chen, S., Liu, K.K., Davdand, P., Dong, G.H., Yang, B. Y., 2024. Greenspace and human microbiota: a systematic review. *Environ. Int.* 187, 108662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108662>.